

Results of the FARM VALUE research project

Farm value and farm transfer: perspectives from economics and sociology

The research project **FARM_VALUE** ('Farm value and farm transfer: perspectives from economics and sociology'), funded by the French National Research Agency (ANR) **between 2017 and 2021**, brought together several teams of economists and sociologists **to improve our understanding of how farm value is calculated, to take into account the diversity of the components of this value, and to link value to the process of farm transfer.**

The project teams

<i>Research Unit</i>	<i>Institute</i>	<i>City</i>
Bordeaux Sciences Economiques (BSE) (Project coordination)	INRAE	Bordeaux
SMART	INRAE	Rennes
PjSE	INRAE	Paris
Territories	VetAgro Sup	Clermont-Ferrand
CERAG	Grenoble Alpes University	Grenoble
LASA	University of Bourgogne-Franche-Comté	Besançon
CERLIS	University Paris Cité	Paris
AGIR	ENSAT	Toulouse

Project objectives and approaches

The value of a farm: a central point in the transfer process

The aim of the FARM_VALUE research project was to shed light on transfers of farms, focusing in particular on the role of farm value in this process.

From a global point of view, while the number of farms has continued to diminish over the years, the issue of farm transfer is inextricably linked to the renewal of the productive capacity of French agriculture. For farmers, the transfer of their farm is a stage of major importance in their lives. It is the measure of the success of a lifetime of work, and results in the perpetuation of what has been built. Contrary to what one might think, the value of a farm is not immediately available, nor given, for example, by its market price. This value must be constructed, and several approaches are possible, sometimes producing very different results. Moreover, this value incorporates not only economic aspects but also other components. It is therefore of utmost importance to understand the different valuation methods, particularly when they are used at the time of transfer.

Complementary quantitative and qualitative approaches combining economics and sociology

In this project the disciplines of economics and sociology were mobilised, separately but also together to enrich the results and points of view. For the statistical analyses, the economic approaches drew on existing structural and accounting databases (containing data on thousands of farms from the French Farm Accountancy Data Network-FADN ('Réseau d'Information Comptable Agricole'-RICA), or the French social funds for farmers ('Mutualité Sociale Agricole'-MSA)), and more precise data on the transfer process collected through a specific quantitative survey carried out within the framework of the project on approximately 200 farmers, 87% of whom were successors and 13% transferors. The sociological approaches drew on the results of a hundred or so qualitative interviews with successors, transferors and prescribers. The project focused on dairy and beef farming in three French sub-regions: Puy-de-Dôme, Doubs and Ille-et-Vilaine.

Main results of the project

The results of the project show that **the transfer of farms is complex** and goes beyond the mere transfer of production factors (land, buildings, equipment, livestock, etc.). Intangible assets are also concerned, and the implications are family-related, patrimonial, legal, economic, social and entrepreneurial.

The main result of the project is that there are **large differences in value depending on the main agricultural production of the farm, the valuation method used, the existence and nature of the links between transferors and successors, the size of the land and the farmhouse, and the type of prescriber of this value**, i.e., actors who advise and accompany farmers (agricultural advisors, accountants, land and agricultural experts, notaries, etc.).

With regard to the valuation of the farm itself, the main methods are based on the estimation of cash flows and the assets of farms (via the assets entered in the balance sheet). They yield two categories of evaluation: on the one hand, an approach that measures economic value, which results from the accumulation of discounted cash flows over a defined period (9 years for example) and which indicates the value of the investment necessary for the takeover; and on the other hand, an approach that measures the asset value of the farm, which results from the accumulated value of its various assets. It emerges that, in relation to the farm's turnover or agricultural area, the economic value is generally higher than the asset value for the majority of main production types. On the other hand, this logic is reversed for farms specialising in meat production, with asset values generally higher than economic values. Our work has made it possible to test alternative evaluation techniques, such as valuation using multiples. This method, which divides the value of the farm by an income proxy such as gross operating surplus (GOS), shows that a French dairy farm has, on average, an economic value, as well as an asset value (excluding land), equivalent to 1.5 years of income.

When we look at the assets of active farmers over 50 years of age, we find that the average gross value of these assets is above 800,000 Euros due to the sustained process of investment in professional assets. However, unlike most self-employed people (craftsmen, businessmen), farmers sell (or pass on) a larger part of their professional assets at the time of their retirement. This results in a very significant decrease in their total gross assets (on average close to 400,000 Euros for retired farmers), a phenomenon which is generally not observed for other self-employed people. This decrease is due to debt reduction, donations and to the way in which professional agricultural assets are valued.

Value and transmission of the farm: a cross-section of economics and sociology

Our study of farmers' assets before and after retirement highlights the particular role played by land assets at the time of transfer. Land is increasingly considered as a store of value, or as a means of maintaining an emotional link with the local territory, or as a lever for maintaining a small-scale agricultural activity. Moreover, the house of the transferor has a significant value which must be taken into account in the farm transfer process, and is an integral part of the representation of the value of the farm for the transferor. It significantly increases the value of the business property transferred.

Our work also focused on the cost of taking over the farm, which is an important factor for access to the profession. The analysis was based on farmers' applications for farm settlement subsidies for the period 2007 to 2017. The results show that, while the cost of the takeover is around 80,000 Euros, investments are implemented in the first four years at an additional cost of almost 200,000 Euros. The total cost of the takeover depends, however, on the size, legal status and type of main production of the farm, as well as on the gender and education level of the transferors and successors.

The stakeholders involved in the transfer process, referred to here as prescribers, are numerous and varied. They contribute to defining the scope of what is being transferred and the value of the farm's shares. They provide expertise in evaluating certain complex assets such as buildings, the market for which remains opaque, unlike the market for agricultural equipment. It emerges that the family is often the source of constraints in the transfer process, as the value is high and the composition of the assets complex. The transfer phase also appears to raise legal and tax issues for which families are not always prepared. The role of advisors is therefore also becoming crucial in providing legal and tax support in the transfer process, which is complex because it involves not only the farmer but also all co-heirs. Legal and tax advice structures tend to create companies to facilitate the transfer to the farmer's children while securing the functionality of professional assets for the successor.

Finally, the results of the project reveal that the estimate of the value of the property transferred by transferors is negatively correlated with the value they assign to the successor, whether he/she is from the family or not. The more positive the successor's assessment of his/her ability to perpetuate the business, the more likely the transferor is to make arrangements to reduce the price of the farm. Transfers outside the family framework thus bring to light new forms of collaboration in agriculture between the transferor and the successor. This is what appears in many of the cases observed, where the transferor temporarily becomes an employee of the successor. This type of collaboration allows the transferor to transfer the farm earlier than at retirement age while remaining in employment. It also gives the transferor more time to pass on his/her knowledge to the non-family successor. These social interactions also play an important role in the assessment of the value of the farm and its sustainability.

This combination of economic and sociological analyses highlights the **crucial role of collaboration between the transferor and the successor**. This collaboration ensures better control of the farm and limits drops in performance, generally measured as occurring in the 3 to 5 years following the arrival of the successor.

Project publications

All publications (articles, dissemination notes) written in the framework of the FARM_VALUE research project are freely available on https://zenodo.org/communities/farm_value.

A selection of publications is presented below:

Jeanneau, P., Desjeux, Y., Enjolras, G., Latruffe, L. 2022. Farm valuation: A comparison of methods for French farms. *Agribusiness*, online first. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/agr.21752>

Bertoni, D., Cavicchioli, D., Latruffe, L. 2022. Impact of business transfer on economic performance: The case of Italian family farms. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, online first. <https://www.inderscience.com/info/ingeneral/forthcoming.php?jcode=ijesb>

Paroissien, E., Latruffe, L., Piet, L. 2021. Early exit from business, performance and neighbours' influence: A study of farmers in France. *European Review of Agricultural Economics*, 48(5): 1132-1161. <https://academic.oup.com/erae/article/48/5/1132/6146008>

Jacques-Jouvenot, D., Sposito-Tourier, M., Casagrande, C. 2021. « PARCE QU'IL LE VAUT BIEN ! » L'estimation d'une exploitation agricole et de son successeur (Franche-Comt). *Etudes Rurales*, 208: 124-145. <https://journals.openedition.org/etudesrurales/27899>

Jacques-Jouvenot, D. 2021. Le vrai prix de la transmission agricole. *En direct, le journal de la recherche et du transfert de l'arc jurassien*, 294. <https://endirect.univ-fcomte.fr/publication/le-vrai-prix-de-la-transmission-agricole/>

Enjolras, G., Sanfilippo, G., Soliwoda, M. 2021. The determinants of the capital structure of farms: Evidence for France and Poland. *Baltic Journal of Economics*, 21(2): 112-132. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1406099X.2021.1972587>

Enjolras, G., Sanfilippo, G. 2019. La structure du capital des exploitations agricoles franaises. *Economie Rurale*, 369: 5-20. <https://journals.openedition.org/economierurale/6893>

Desjeux, Y., Jeanneau, P., Enjolras, G., Latruffe, L. 2018. Enqute sur l'utilisation des mthodes d'valuation de la valeur des exploitations agricoles : rsum des rsultats. Note INRA, 6pp. <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-02784914/>

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